

Effect of whole-language approach on tenth graders' learning outcomes and motivations for biographical text writing

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 18(03), 1131–1136

Publication history: Received on 30 April 2023; revised on 19 June 2023; accepted on 21 June 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.3.1097>

Abstract

This research explores: (1) students' learning outcomes and motivations for biographical text writing before using the whole-language approach, (2) students' learning outcomes and motivations for biographical text writing after using the whole-language approach, and (3) the effect of the whole-language approach on tenth graders' learning outcomes and motivations for biographical text writing at SMK Negeri 3 Gorontalo Utara. The achieved indicators were: (1) Listing the main points of information, (2) Analyzing language in biographical texts, (3) Writing biographical texts about certain figures by paying attention to the content, encompassing educational background, career, and struggles, and (4) Giving oral responses to the text content. Data tests were carried out for data normality, variance homogeneity, and hypothesis. The pretest and post-test scores were 65.97 and 85.03, respectively. Thus, the hypothesis stating that there was an interaction between learning outcomes and motivations and could not stand independently was accepted. Accordingly, preciseness in choosing learning approaches significantly impacted biographical text writing.

Keywords: Whole-Language Effect; Learning Outcome; Learning Motivation; Research

1. Introduction

Writing biographical texts is writing the history of a particular figure. In writing the texts, as such, we should find information from electronic or printed media and even interviewing the figure concerned. In practicing biographical text writing, we should be self-acknowledged of all information in relation to the object as our biographical study. According to Nugraha (2013:1), a biographical text refers to the history of life of an individual. It can be in the form of words, several sentence lines, or books written in an exquisite narrating style that brings readers closer to the character.

A biography, by definition, narrates the history of life of a person. It is mindful of facts and concepts, describing why it is interesting to read, and develops intimacy between the figure addressed and readers. And yet, in learning biographical and historical text writing, several factors are still influential, breeding difficulties in attaining excellent outcomes. I am interested in researching biographical texts as based on my experiences of discussing or learning biographies made by students, the texts are interesting because addressing historical figures.

Students should know historical figures well. Accordingly, students can also learn the figures while learning biographical text writing. I chose the specific school and the same texts, i.e., biographical texts because, building on my interview with students and the teacher, students at the school lacked motivation for learning. It encouraged me to carry out relevant research.

I also found that students were poorly accustomed to writing habit, environment, and wording. I am expecting that students will be able to describe a figure in concert with the elements, structure, and language characteristics of

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biographical texts. As such, I propose a solution of delivering biographical text writing materials to students using the whole-language approach.

I am expecting to help students learn and practice producing a good piece of writing in good agreement with the Indonesian grammar using the whole-language approach. Santosa et al. (2008:216) define whole-language as an approach to language learning grounded on constructivism. Using the approach, language is delivered in a whole and unsegregated avenue, and listening, speaking, reading, and writing are delivered in an integrated fashion, enabling students to perceive language as one unit. I endeavor to make the approach compatible with the intended biographical text writing materials.

2. Research method

This experimental research used a quantitative approach. I proposed a hypothesis to be tested for the acceptability. A hypothesis described the correlation between two or more variables. It aimed to examine whether a certain variable was associated with others or whether a certain variable was caused/affected by others. In addition, it measured and tested the causal relationship between two or more variables using an inferential (inductive) statistical analysis).

Table 1 Research Design

Learning Method	Whole-Language Approach	Discovery-Learning Approach
Learning motivation		
High	A1B1	A2B1
Low	A1B2	A2B2

2.1. Data Collection Technique

The data collection techniques were documentation, interview, and test. In other words, I employed test and non-test data collection techniques (observation, questionnaire, and pictorial documents). The techniques measured biographical text writing skills using direct teaching methods.

2.2. Data Analysis Technique

Data quantitative were in the form of cognitive learning outcomes analyzed using the descriptive analysis technique, a research method to delineate reality or facts in accordance with the data collected to investigate students' learning outcomes, learning activities, and teachers' activities during the learning. A descriptive analysis examined students' mean scores of biographical text writing learning using the whole-language approach. The statistical descriptive analysis addressed the maximum and minimum scores on the grounds of student motivation levels for biographical text writing learning.

3. Result and discussion

Table 2 Research Data Description

Test	Motivation	N	Min. Score	Max. Score	Mean
Pretest	High	15	70.00	86.00	76.8000
	Low	15	41.00	68.00	55.1333
Post-test	High	15	80.00	98.00	91.3333
	Low	15	70.00	90.00	78.7333

Source: Data Processed Using SPSS 26

3.1. Students' Learning Outcomes and Motivations for Biographical Text Writing Before Using the Whole-Language Approach (Pretest)

A pretest was conducted to collect data on learning outcomes before using the whole-language approach and identify student motivation, either high or low. The teaching-learning process using the whole-language approach was performed in the control class. I delivered a pretest pertaining to biographical text of a famous historical figure, i.e., R. A. Kartini for students. Table 3 demonstrates data on learning outcomes and motivations collected.

Table 3 Students' Learning Outcomes and Motivations Before Using the Whole-Language Approach

No.	Name	Score	Motivation	Category
1	Arya Fitrawan Suleman	45	50	2
2	Cindra Moodu	41	50	2
3	Etriskawati Naniu	55	50	2
4	Fatmawati Antu	61	65	2
5	Firman Dunggio	61	58	2
6	Firna Lambari	68	60	2
7	Hasmawati Patila	70	77	1
8	Karis Agung Tataran	75	78	1
9	Moh. Rizaldi Djauhari	75	77	1
10	Nurul Fath. Saputri Moodu	78	84	1
11	Prasetyo Nelwan Djeko	78	86	1
12	Raditya Gobel	80	80	1
13	Rizal Uwaya	80	82	1
14	Sultan Mahmud Al-Asiari	73	77	1
15	Zakia Jeila Moodu	73	74	1
16	Zulkifli Sanusi	45	48	2
17	Adelia Mooduto	48	48	2
18	Aditnya H. Olli	48	40	2
19	Andri Talipi	55	50	2
20	Aldito Dwi Putra Bobihu	61	65	2
21	Alfian Liputo	68	60	2
22	Fikri Patamani	78	75	1
23	Firman Dayi	83	88	1
24	Hajrin Mooduto	78	80	1
25	Hasbi Bobihu	61	64	2
26	Manda Tangahu	55	50	2
27	Moh. Fikran Yadin Budiko	70	75	1
28	Moh. Riski Dauwango	75	75	1
29	Nirmala	86	89	1
30	Pelista Ladjo	55	50	2

The following parts explained students' learning results and motivations before using the whole-language approach.

3.2. Pretest Results Exhibiting a High Motivation

15 students were identified for having a high learning motivation before using the whole-language approach. The minimum score was 70, and the maximum one was 86. The mean count (\bar{x}) was 76.80.

3.3. Pretest Results Exhibiting a Low Motivation

15 students were identified for having a low learning motivation before using the whole-language approach. The minimum score was 41, and the maximum one was 68. The mean count (\bar{x}) was 55.

3.4. Students' Learning Outcomes and Motivations for Biographical Text Writing After Using the Whole-Language Approach

Before the post-test, we gave students an activity of learning to write a biographical text using the whole-language approach. The learning process was conducted in five stages. The stage covered introduction, main activities, and closing. During the second stage, the teacher implemented the whole-language approach. To begin with, the teacher delivered storytelling techniques. The teacher mentioned and explicated biographical figures students knew, making them listen and more familiarized with them. Next, students were given freedom to choose biographical figures they admired. Students were then instructed to read to list the main information, analyze the language of biographical texts provided by the teacher. The teacher correlated the biographical figures being discussed to students' life experiences. Therefore, students could participate or be motivated. For example, they would likely find motivation from educational background, career, and life journey of the biographical figures the teacher mentioned. The last stage, closing, was where the teacher and students concluded learning materials, and the first party evaluated the materials accepted by students.

3.5. Effect of the Whole-Language Approach on Learning Outcomes and Motivations for Biographical Text Writing Learning

After using the whole-language approach, we identified changes in students' learning outcomes and motivations, as indicated in Table 4.

Table 4 Data on Overall Scores of Students' Learning Outcomes and Motivatoons

Respondent	Student Achievement Score							
	Pretest		Desc.		Post-Test		Desc.	
1	45	50	2	Low	86	73	2	Low
2	41	50	2	Low	86	70	2	Low
3	55	50	2	Low	90	74	2	Low
4	61	65	2	Low	70	65	2	Low
5	61	58	2	Low	78	65	2	Low
6	68	60	2	Low	80	73	2	Low
7	70	77	1	High	73	65	2	Low
8	75	78	1	High	78	74	2	Low
9	75	77	1	High	80	74	2	Low
10	78	84	1	High	98	93	1	High
11	78	86	1	High	95	88	1	High
12	80	80	1	High	95	88	1	High
13	80	82	1	High	98	90	1	High
14	73	77	1	High	73	65	2	Low
15	73	74	1	High	90	84	1	High

16	45	48	2	Low	86	72	2	Low
17	48	48	2	Low	80	77	1	High
18	48	40	2	Low	86	80	1	High
19	55	50	2	Low	93	88	1	Low
20	61	65	2	Low	70	66	2	Low
21	68	60	2	Low	78	65	2	Low
22	78	75	1	High	80	74	2	Low
23	83	88	1	High	95	90	1	High
24	78	80	1	High	80	82	1	High
25	61	64	2	Low	93	88	1	High
26	55	50	2	Low	86	88	1	High
27	70	75	1	High	93	86	1	High
28	75	75	1	High	73	73	2	Low
29	86	89	1	High	98	96	1	High
30	55	50	2	Low	90	86	1	High

From Table 4, students exhibited positive changes. Using the whole-language approach, students develop a higher understanding of the learning given and were able to gain more knowledge, engendering significantly different post-test scores from the pretest ones. Students' learning outcomes and motivations before using the whole-language approach were scored 76.80000 and 55.1333 by average, respectively. Meanwhile, after using the approach, the outcomes and motivations increased to 91.3333 and 78.7333 by average, respectively.

4. Conclusion

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) using a significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ generated an F count of 132.863 and an F table of 4.01. Thus, F count > F table, and H₀ was rejected. To sum up, overall, there was a significant difference in learning outcomes of biographical text writing before and after using the whole-language approach. Accordingly, the hypothesis stating that the whole-language approach had a positive impact was accepted, shown by students' mean scores after using the approach higher than that before using it. The post-test and pretest scores were 85.03 and 65.97, respectively.

Building on the statistical descriptive analysis, students' mean score from the post-test after using the whole-language approach with a high motivation was 91.33, and that from the pretest before using the approach with a high motivation was 76.80. As such, a high learning motivation with the whole-language approach would improve students' scores.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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